

1 **Low intrinsic carrier density LSMO/Alq3/AlOx/Co organic spintronic devices**

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10 **Abstract**

11 The understanding of spin injection and transport in organic spintronic devices is still incomplete, with some experiments
12 showing magnetoresistance and others not detecting it. We have investigated the transport properties of a large number
13 of tris-(8-hydroxyquinoline)aluminum-based organic spintronic devices with an electrical resistance greater than 5MΩ
14 that did not show magnetoresistance. Their transport properties could be described satisfactorily by known models for
15 organic semiconductors. At high voltages (>2 V), the results were well described by the model of space charge limited
16 current with a Poole-Frenkel mobility. At low voltages (~0.1 V), which are those at which the spin valve behavior is
17 usually observed, the charge transport was modelled by nearest neighbor hopping in intra-gap impurity levels, with a
18 charge carrier density of $n_0=(1.44\pm 0.21)\times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ at room temperature. Such low carrier density can explain why no
19 magnetoresistance was observed.

1 Despite intense efforts since the inception of organic spintronics, the understanding of spin injection and transport in
2 organic semiconductors is still incomplete. Organic spintronics brings together the advantages of spintronics[1], that is
3 the ability to generate and manipulate spin polarized currents, with those of organic materials, namely the low spin
4 scattering rate of charge carriers, which is due to the relatively low spin-orbit coupling[2] and hyperfine interaction[3] in
5 these materials. Several works on ferromagnetic electrode/organic semiconductor/ferromagnetic electrode (FM/OS/FM)
6 organic spintronic devices reported the presence of giant magnetoresistance(GMR)[4]–[7] while others did not observe
7 it[8]. This type of device has great applicative potential in data storage[9] and in multifunctional applications where
8 memory and computational capabilities on the same device are desired[10], [11]. Experimental[12]–[19] and
9 theoretical[20][21] efforts were devoted to the understanding of the role of the interface and of the OS in spin transport;
10 some results suggested that spin injection in the OS was actually taking place [22], [23].

11 One of the crucial outstanding questions in organic spintronics is the absence of the Hanle effect (i.e. spin precession),
12 which used to be considered the ultimate proof of spin injection[24]. While spin precession and the Hanle effect were
13 observed in inorganic materials[25][26], new insights were spurred by the finding that they were not detected in tris-(8-
14 hydroxyquinoline)aluminum (Alq3)-based organic spintronic devices[27], [28]. This was confirmed by spin pumping
15 experiments[29], which circumvent the possible artifacts due to transport or tunneling across hot spots or defects in the
16 devices.

17 The unexpected absence of the Hanle effect in Alq3-based organic spintronics devices demands a fresh understanding of
18 charge and spin transport in this OS. The study of charge transport in Alq3 received great attention since the publication
19 of the seminal paper on organic emitting diodes by Tang and Van Slyke[30]; since then, numerous articles on its transport
20 properties have appeared[31]–[36]. None of these earlier studies addressed the Hanle effect. This question was more
21 recently tackled by Yu, who introduced a model in which the exchange interaction between the spin polarized carriers
22 could justify its absence [37], [38]; it also explains why the conductivity mismatch between the electrodes and the OS[39]
23 does not completely disrupt spin injection in OSs.

24 A crucial ingredient for spin transport (and thus GMR) in Yu's model is a sufficiently high charge carrier concentration,
25 namely $n_0 > 2 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The efficiency of the mechanism is compromised at smaller concentrations and no GMR can be
26 observed. In this work we focused in the limiting case of a very low carrier concentration, which is accompanied by
27 negligible GMR. We studied Alq3-based organic spintronic devices with an electrical resistance greater than $5 \text{ M}\Omega$ that
28 did not show a GMR[8]. We analyzed the resistance of a large number of devices and we studied their current voltage
29 characteristics as a function of voltage and as a function of temperature, determining the transport mechanisms at high (>
30 2 V) and low ($\sim 100 \text{ mV}$) voltages.

1 Devices consisted in a $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ (LSMO)/Alq3/AlO_x/Co vertical structure; the active area was either $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ or
2 $1 \times 0.2 \text{ mm}^2$. Figure 1a) shows their general layout. The 20 nm thick LSMO film was deposited by channel spark ablation
3 from a stoichiometric target on a matching SrTiO_3 substrate in a 4×10^{-2} mbar O_2 atmosphere at a rate of $0.1 \text{ \AA/pulse}$ [40].
4 During deposition the substrate was kept at a temperature of $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; the remaining layers were fabricated at room
5 temperature. The Alq3 was deposited at rate of $0.13 \text{ \AA/s}$ at a base pressure of 10^{-8} mbar; prior to Alq3 deposition, the
6 LSMO film was annealed at $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30' in vacuum in order to eliminate water and other contaminants that could come
7 from exposure to air. AlO_x was obtained by evaporating a 2.4 nm thick Al film and by oxidizing it for 15' in a pure O_2
8 atmosphere at pressure of 100 mbar; this layer is known to improve the quality of the Alq3/Co interface[12], [41] and of
9 the Co film[42]. It also protects the Alq3 top interface from possible damage cause by electron gun evaporation[43].
10 Finally, a 20 nm thick Co film was deposited by e-gun evaporation at base pressure of 10^{-9} mbar and at rate of $0.2 \text{ \AA/s}$.

11 Organic spintronic devices can show GMR, i.e. a resistance that depends on the relative orientations of the magnetization
12 of the electrodes; Table SI and Table SII in the Supplementary Information show a survey of such results available from
13 the literature and Figure S2 shows a comparison with the data obtained from our laboratory. In this work we concentrated
14 on high resistance devices that do not show GMR (Figure S1, Supplementary Information).

15 Most works in the literature have not focused on determining the exact charge transport mechanism in organic spin valves.
16 An effective approach is to investigate the behavior of the resistance as a function of temperature. Results from the
17 literature are inconclusive on this matter (see Table SII in the Supporting Information): data compatible with
18 semiconductive, metallic and tunneling transport can be found. Concerning the nature of the current-voltage(IV)
19 characteristics, they are non-linear in most of the current literature, which is compatible both with tunneling across a
20 barrier and with transport inside a semiconductor.

21 Figure 1b) shows that the resistance of our devices loosely depends on the thickness of the organic layer. Both the data
22 obtained from the literature and those obtained from the devices fabricated in house show that devices with a nominally
23 equal thickness of OS can show a different normalized electrical resistance (Supplementary Information, Figure S2). This
24 variability is routinely observed also in organic magnetoresistance devices[44], [45]. The reasons for this are not clear,
25 but they can be tentatively ascribed to the high sensitivity of the LSMO/OS interface to even small changes in the
26 fabrication parameters. This makes it difficult to give a firm estimate of the thickness dependence of the resistance.

27 Figure 2 shows the IV characteristics at different temperatures of a LSMO/Alq3 (60 nm)/AlO_x/Co device. Above a
28 threshold voltage (i.e. $V \gtrsim 2 \text{ V}$), the current shows a power law dependence on the applied bias. The exponent of the
29 power law decreases as the temperature is increased. This behavior is consistent with several models of current injection

1 into an organic semiconductor, such as interface limited current (ILC) [32], trapped charge limited current (TCLC) [31]
2 and Mott-Gurney space charge limited current with a field dependent Poole-Frenkel mobility (MG-PF)[33].

3 Quantitative results were obtained by fitting these models to the data (see Supporting Information, Transport Models
4 section for further details). At 100 K, the MG-PF model fitting gave an activation energy of $\Delta E = 0.214 \pm 0.001$ eV and a
5 “built-in” voltage $V_{bi} = 7.08 \pm 0.05$ V. The value found for ΔE was in agreement with the values found in the literature
6 and V_{bi} was somewhat larger[33], [47], but compatible with the current-voltage characteristics that can be found therein.
7 As the temperature was increased, the activation energy ΔE increased. The values varied between samples by
8 approximately 10%.

9 The message from these data at high voltages ($V \geq 2$ V) is that conduction was taking place in the intrinsic transport
10 levels of Alq3, namely in the highest occupied molecular level (HOMO) or in the lowest unoccupied molecular level
11 (LUMO). This is the standard picture of conduction in molecular semiconductors, and is especially relevant for organic
12 light emitting diodes, in which light emission is taking place exactly because electrons in the LUMO and holes in the
13 HOMO recombine to give out a photon.

14 At small voltages (~ 100 mV) the conduction regime changed. The study of charge transport at ~ 100 mV is necessary
15 because most organic spintronic experiments were carried out at such voltages (see Table SI in Supporting Information).
16 Transport at these voltages is thermally activated, as demonstrated by Figure 3, where the resistance measured at 100 mV
17 is plotted as a function of $1/T$; the fit of the Arrhenius law $\ln R \propto \Delta E / (k_B T)$ gives $\Delta E = (3.41 \pm 0.09)$ meV. Such temperature
18 dependence is indicative of nearest neighbor hopping. These results are in agreement with those from Jiang et al.[6], where
19 no GMR was observed.

20 IV characteristics at low voltages (± 0.125 V) were also measured at several temperatures, from 100 K up to 300 K; the
21 inset in Figure 3 shows the slope of the IVs at such temperatures. These IV characteristics follow a power law $J \propto V^\alpha$, with
22 α decreasing monotonously from ~ 2 at 100 K to ~ 1 at 300 K. A slope of $\alpha = 2$ corresponds the Mott-Gurney law which
23 governs space charge limited currents (SCLC):

$$24 \quad J_{SCLC} = \frac{9}{8} \mu_n \varepsilon \frac{V^2}{d^3} \quad (1)$$

25 where J_{SCLC} is the current density, μ_n is the mobility, ε is the dielectric constant, V is the applied voltage and d is the
26 thickness of the OS. This means that at 100 K carriers are mostly injected and that intrinsic, thermally activated carriers
27 can be neglected. At 300 K, $J \propto V$, i.e. transport was ohmic:

$$1 \quad J_{OHM} = \frac{q \mu_n n_0 V}{d} \quad (2)$$

2 where n_0 is the carrier density and q is the carrier's charge. In this case transport happens via intrinsic, thermally activated
3 carriers[3]. From this equation one obtains a carrier density of $n_0=(1.44\pm 0.21)\times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, (see the section "Determination
4 of the carrier concentration" in the Supporting Information); since at lower temperatures conduction becomes space
5 charge limited, the carrier density can only decrease as temperature decreases.

6 The fact that charge transport occurred at these very small voltages means that it was taking place neither in the HOMO
7 nor in the LUMO of Alq3. These energy levels are too far from the Fermi level of LSMO or Co to account for any
8 meaningful charge transport[13], [48]. Our findings demonstrate that transport was instead occurring in intragap levels
9 induced by the presence of impurities which, based on the available evidence, we tentatively attribute to oxygen
10 doping[49]. The presence of intragap states was also inferred from previous work on similar devices[50]: in that case a
11 process similar to thermally stimulated current indicated the presence of trap states in the conduction gap of Alq3, in
12 analogy to what was observed in the present devices. Oxygen doping causes holes to be present in the gap of Alq3
13 transport levels. At sufficiently high concentration these carriers can form an impurity band[38]. Trap levels can also be
14 induced by exposure of the organic film to x-ray radiation emitted during electron-gun deposition of the Co layer[43] but
15 we exclude this possibility because of the presence of the AlOx barrier.

16 The value of the charge carrier concentration has crucial consequences for spin transport. In Yu's model[37] the spin
17 diffusion constant D_S is given by the sum of the charge hopping-mediated spin diffusion constant D_H and the exchange-
18 mediated one D_E : $D_S = D_H + D_E$. The exchange interaction originates from the electron wave function overlap and can be
19 estimated by:

$$20 \quad \bar{J} = 0.821 \frac{e^2}{\epsilon \xi} \left(\frac{\bar{R}}{\xi} \right)^{5/2} e^{-2\bar{R}/\xi} \quad (3)$$

21 where ϵ is the dielectric constant, ξ is the polaron localization length, $\bar{R}$ is the average interpolaron distance and e is the
22 electron charge; importantly, this exchange interaction preserves the total spin and does not contribute to spin scattering.

23 The exchange-mediated spin diffusion constant is given by:

$$24 \quad D_E = \sqrt{\pi/12} \bar{J} \bar{R} \quad (4)$$

25 Clearly D_E depends on the charge carrier concentration n via $\bar{R} = 1/n^3$. Their relative importance depends steeply on the
26 carrier density n . While the contribution of D_E is negligible for $n < 2 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, D_E becomes 10^8 greater than D_H for $n > 10^{19}$
27 cm^{-3} , making spin transport possible. In other words, for $n < 2 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ spin diffusion is due to the very inefficient charge

1 hopping mechanism which is hindered by the conductivity mismatch problem, making it negligible; this explains why no
2 GMR was observed.

3 In theory, spin precession is possible in charge carriers in these devices, but GMR cannot be used as a means to detect it.
4 As a side comment, the low density of carriers also explains why no magnetoconductance was observed, as the three main
5 models for this phenomenon, namely the electron-hole pair model[51], the bipolaron model[52] and the triplet-polaron
6 model[53], require a sufficiently high density of charge carriers.

7 In conclusion, we studied LSMO/Alq3/AlOx/Co organic spintronic devices in the limiting case of very low charge carrier
8 concentration. We detected the distinguishing features of conduction in organic semiconductors, i.e. a strongly decreasing
9 resistance as the temperature is increased and highly non-linear IV characteristics above a threshold voltage[7]. Overall
10 our findings confirm that charge transport in these devices is well described by accepted models of conduction in organic
11 semiconductors. The thickness dependence of the resistance could not be assessed quantitatively due to the variability
12 that is typical in this type of devices. We demonstrated that at low voltages, i.e. in the regime of interest for organic
13 spintronics, transport was taking place in intra-gap impurity levels; we tentatively identify oxygen as the impurity. The
14 charge carrier concentration was $n_0=(1.44\pm 0.21)\times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, too small for the exchange mechanism proposed by Yu to
15 function. These results help build a more precise understanding of spin transport in organic semiconductors. In the present
16 devices, the carrier concentration is insufficient to sustain the exchange interaction and spin diffusion happens via the
17 more mundane charge hopping. This mechanism is very inefficient and is unable to sustain a spin polarized current over
18 the thickness of the organic semiconductor. This also explains why no GMR was observed.

19 **Supplementary material**

20 The supplementary material contains a comparison with devices that show GMR, data fits for charge transport, tables
21 summarizing the results from literature and a determination of the charge carriers' density.

22 **Acknowledgements**

23 We would like to acknowledge the encouraging advice given by Dr.Zhi-Gang Yu and the invaluable technical assistance
24 of Mr.Federico Bona.

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2 Figure 1: a) General layout of the organic spintronic devices studied in this work. In the electrical measurements carried
 3 out on the devices fabricated in house, the ground is applied to the top, Co electrode. Electrical measurements were carried
 4 out in a 4-probe configuration. b) Thickness dependence of the resistance of LSMO/Alq3/Co devices in the high resistance
 5 class, which show no GMR. The resistance shows a power-law like dependence on the thickness, but no quantitative
 6 estimate could be performed due to the data scatter. The resistance was measured at -100mV applied to the LSMO. The
 7 shaded area is a guide to the eye.

8

Figure 2: Current voltage characteristic of a LSMO/Alq₃ (60 nm)/AlO_x/Co HR device belonging to the high resistance class. Above a threshold voltage the devices show a power-law behavior. The exponent decreases as the temperature is decreased. This behavior corresponds to charge transport in the organic (see Supporting Information for a more detailed discussion). Inset: Dependence of the power law exponent m of the IV characteristics on temperature. m increases as the temperature is decreased: $m \propto 1/T$. This behavior is compatible with models of injection limited, trapped charge limited and space charge limited charge transport in organic semiconductors; it is observed in all HR devices.

Figure 3: Temperature dependence of a LSMO/Alq3 (300 nm)/AlOx/Co HR device measured at small voltages (± 100 mV); in this range the IV characteristic is ohmic. The data fit an Arrhenius law, indicating that transport is thermally activated, with an activation energy of $\Delta E = (3.41 \pm 0.09) \text{ meV}$. The inset shows the slope of the IV characteristics of a LSMO/Alq3 (40 nm)/AlOx/Co HR device measured at ± 100 mV; the line is a guide to the eye. The slope decreases from ~ 2 at 100 K, indicative of space charge limited current, to ~ 1 at 300 K, that is indicative of ohmic transport.

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